

FORMATION OF THE SPHERE OF CULTURE AND ENLIGHTENMENT AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE

Matyakubova F.B.

Teacher at the Institute for Advanced Studies of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, major

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13118984>

Abstract. *In the article, methods for the development of the sphere of culture and enlightenment among young people and the ways they can be demonstrated are discussed. Youth need to be educated and upbrought so that they can succeed. This article will be useful for young people and their parents and will help them understand their place in the world.*

Keywords: *national culture, globalization, enlightenment, historical, spirit, tourism, art, management, disenlightenment.*

There are several ways to form the sphere of culture and enlightenment among young people. First of all, it is necessary to prepare appropriate and advanced educational technologies and textbooks for young people. These technologies provide morale and culture enhancement for young people. Secondly, it is necessary to ensure the expediency of organizing a lot of talk, discussion and research in order to form the field of enlightenment and culture among young people. These activities help to increase the enlightenment of young people, to develop their thinking and reflection. Also, in order to form the field of enlightenment and culture among the youth, community organizations, schools and teachers should organize and manage many circles on a large scale. These activities ensure that the youth grow up in an environment that provides enlightenment and culture. In addition, it is also important to provide software tools and programs for the formation of the sphere of enlightenment and culture among young people. These programs help young people to increase their interest in culture and develop their own learning tools.

We are moving towards building a prosperous life, spiritual growth, and an enlightened society where human rights and freedoms are guaranteed. For this purpose, we will continue our reforms in the spiritual sphere, bypassing all trials and difficulties. However, there are not all issues that await the solution in spiritual and educational work. For example, major changes, the national idea, created by defining the theoretical basis of the new society, is the first issue. Because it is known from the history of the world that any people or nation united around a single goal, a single idea, has achieved the development of that state. But there are still people among us who do not understand the state of spirituality, do not know whether it is necessary or not, and do not want to talk about the national idea. Some people mean the ideologies of the old regimes when they say the national idea. It is known that the issue of youth, which is considered an integral part of society, has always interested philosophers, political scientists, lawyers, historians, pedagogues, psychologists, writers, poets. Philosophers study the place of young people in social life, lawyers study their educational rights and legal guarantees, historians study their place in the history of society, psychologists study their condition – mental character, pedagogues study the main issues of youth education, political scientists study the role of young people in social life. The reason why so much attention is being paid to the issue of young people is that they differ from adults in their enthusiasm, perspective, desire for knowledge, inquisitiveness and other characteristics. Young people enrich the enlightenment, culture, spirituality, traditions and customs left by their

ancestors, take certain places in the history of social life with new initiatives and progress. For this purpose, the society invests its youth in its future by acquiring knowledge, acquiring a certain profession, observing their own world views, developing their physical maturity and spiritually healthy childhood. “The people of the past,” wrote Abu Nasr Farabi, “leave the pleasure they had from generation to generation through the generation after them”. It can be seen from these lines that the past generation bequeaths the best wealth to the next generation, and this legacy is preserved and continued by the youth. While thinking about the spirituality and perspective of young people, we should not forget the many programs for young people in world religions such as Zoroastrianism, Buddhism, Christianity and Islam, which are among the great values. Apart from these, each society educates young people, enriches their spirituality, and forms their worldview based on their conditions, characteristics, and social content. In turn, young people apply the experience they have gained from adults and work based on the doctrines they like. They take part in the relevant work, preserving their favorite traditions and values, discarding or changing aspects that are destructive for the development of society. The representatives of classical philosophy emphasized that history is a change of generations, and that each generation uses the wealth, productive forces, and materials of the ancestors who lived before it, and at the same time changes the old conditions by means of its activities and adjusts them to its own interests. It is this fact of life that is proven in the first decades of our country’s independence, as well as today. More than 31 years have passed since our country gained independence. Fundamental reforms and democratic changes implemented in all spheres in this short period are bearing fruit. The strategy of New Uzbekistan developed by the head of our state and the principle “From the strategy of actions to the strategy of development” put forward in it is recognized as an important idea of social development. This principle is recognized by the international community as an effective means of serving the people. So, in the words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, “The new development strategy of Uzbekistan has started a new stage of our national development. From now on, we will organize our activities on the basis of the principle of ‘man-society-state.’ In the implementation of its tasks in this regard, to achieve the publicity and openness of the work carried out on the further development of the field of spirituality and enlightenment, and to ensure systematicity, scientificity and consistency in the social-spiritual, scientific-educational and educational-spiritual spheres. It is intended to pay special attention to the provision. At the moment, it is necessary to ensure the moral integrity of citizens, ensure equal and mutually beneficial relations between them, free way of thinking, respect for human rights, national and universal values and development of diversity of views, negative impact on human spirit and maturity. Cultivating an intolerant mood towards secretive ideas and doctrines is one of the urgent tasks in this regard. It is known that “according to many thousands of years of human experience, any fundamental renewal, revolutionary change cannot happen without knowledge, spirituality, culture. This is evidenced by the events of all Renaissance periods. That’s why, with the achievement of independence in our country, special attention was paid to this issue. The work aimed at the implementation of the priority goals and tasks in the field of radical reform of this industry and bringing it to a new level is of particular importance.” On December 22, 2023, an extended meeting of the Council of Spirituality and Enlightenment of the Republic was held under the chairmanship of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. In it, our head of state emphasized that we have set clear goals for ourselves in the “Uzbekistan 2030” strategy and have reached the goal high. In accordance with this strategy, it was noted that by 2030 it is planned

to increase the volume of the gross domestic product by 2 times to 160 billion dollars, and the amount of income per capita to reach 4 thousand dollars on average. You are all aware that the conference on the theme “Jadids: ideas of national identity, independence and statehood” held in our capital aroused great interest and attention among the world scientific and cultural community. 45 billion soums annually to support spirituality and creativity is allocating funds. About 200,000 books were distributed free of charge as part of the “Sharing education” and “Book caravan” campaigns. More than 11,000 media products were prepared by the Republican Spirituality and Enlightenment Center and its regional divisions. From 100 billion soums annually to the industry from 2024 Allocation of funds was emphasized.

The main criteria of our activity in the spiritual sphere is to inculcate the idea of New Uzbekistan, which is currently being promoted, into the hearts of our multi-ethnic nation, to unite them around this noble idea, to strengthen the spirit of desire for the future, creativity, initiative.

Therefore, taking into account the regional, professional and age characteristics of our population, it is necessary to take measures to bring the spiritual and educational activities and promotion activities to a completely new level.

As mentioned above, we live in the era of globalization, surrounded by various ideological threats. In such circumstances, we should pay attention to the issue of the level of development of the dynamics of changes manifested in the spiritual life of our country and its impact on the national characteristics of our people. In accordance with these opinions, it is necessary to note the active participation of women in society and state management as an urgent issue of today. As they say, “a healthy mother gives birth to a healthy child”, the importance of mothers in the development of children in our society is incomparable. The socio-political processes prevailing in the world and the historical necessity that have arisen create the necessary foundations for the creation and implementation of practical activity programs that define today and tomorrow in the spiritual and educational sphere of our country.

REFERENCES

1. Bekmurodov M. Begmatov A. National mentality and spirituality. T.: Adolat, 2002.
2. Joraev N. Moral strategy of Uzbekistan. T.: Ma’naviyat, 2016.-32 p.
3. Spirituality: an explanatory dictionary of the main concepts Compiler and responsible editor Q. Nazarov. T.: NMIU named after G’. Ghulam, 2009. B. 678 Abu Nasr Farabi. A city of virtuous people. Tashkent, Abdulla Qadiri “People’s Heritage” publishing house, 1993. 190.
4. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. New Uzbekistan in 2022 On the development strategy for 2026 (collection of normative legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2022, No. 6. www.lex.uz)
5. Mavrulov A. “Culture and the Third Renaissance or by the incomparable will and command of conscience...” New Uzbekistan newspaper, December 10, 2021.